

SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL ASPECTS OF FIGHTING CYBERFRAUD AND CYBERTERRORISM

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Abstract: this article analyzes the essence and conceptual foundations of the concept of cyber security, as well as socio-philosophical aspects of combating cyber fraud and cyber terrorism.

Keywords: digital technologies, cyber security, security, information security, threat, cyber war, cyber fraud, cyber terrorism.

It has been a long time since cybercrime, which is mentioned in new forms, has entered the list of global problems of our century. We cannot turn a blind eye to the fact that it poses a great threat to the lives of mankind by spreading known virus programs, hacking passwords, embezzling funds from credit cards and other bank details, as well as spreading illegal information, especially defamatory, morally corrupt information through the Internet. .

The concept of "cybercrime" is the use of information and communication technologies to create terror in the virtual network, viruses and other malicious programs, preparation and distribution of illegal information, mass distribution of e-mails (spam), hacker attack, illegal access to websites, fraud. , data integrity and copyright violations, theft of credit card numbers and bank details (phishing and pharming) and various other offenses[1].

At this point, it should be noted that the scale of cyber terrorism and its danger to the life of society is also increasing. Cyber-terrorist act (cyber-attack) is a political cause, carried out with the help of computers and information communication tools, which poses a direct or potential threat to people's life and health, can cause or cause great damage to material objects, and is the beginning or goal of socially dangerous consequences. . The attractiveness of using cyberspace for modern terrorists is due to the fact that carrying out a cyberattack does not require large financial costs[2].

According to the experts' conclusion, this is done by influencing the minds of citizens under the guise of promoting the development of developing countries, under the guise of establishing universal democratic principles, and subjugating them to their goals in various ways. » attempts to use are increasing [3].

Because the role of "interference" in the internal affairs of a sovereign state has not been fully studied by social networks available on the Internet, their producers and sponsors, it has not yet been recognized that such "interference" is sometimes against this state. There are no international legal grounds for prosecuting the owners of social networks for inciting the overthrow of the state system on the pages of these networks. However, every criminal act or omission should not go unanswered and unpunished.

Internet sites appear suddenly, often changing their format and then their address. That's why some experts suggest abandoning the initial concepts such as complete openness of the Internet and moving to its new system. The main essence of the new model is to

abandon the anonymity of network users. This made it possible to ensure that the network is more protected from criminal attacks. As an example, we can cite China, which has switched to a closed network system, and Russia, which is preparing for such a process.

In our country, which is integrating into the world community, a consistent state policy on the effective use of information communication technologies, information systems and modern computer technologies is being carried out. Today, modern digital technologies introduced in our country open the door to a number of conveniences and opportunities for our citizens. In addition to this process, there is, of course, the problem of ensuring the security of the digital technologies and information systems being created.

This is one of the most urgent issues - ensuring cyber security, preventing and combating possible cybercrimes. In order to ensure cyber security against cybercrime, which is improving day by day, we can protect ourselves from them, i.e. cyber security, by fulfilling the following basic requirements: training employees in the basics of information security; continuous testing of the vulnerabilities of the software products used; using a reliable antivirus program; using licensed official programs; protecting information systems use factor authentication; adhere to the policy of keeping a strong password when using passwords; regularly encrypt data on computer hard drives. At this point, it should be emphasized that certain tasks are assigned to the competent state agencies that fight against cybercrime in our country.

In particular, they ensure the protection of the security of individuals, society and the state and their interests from external and internal cyber threats, which are implemented or enable the Republic of Uzbekistan and its people through information technologies and communications in the fight against cybercrime, strengthen the rule of law and legitimacy in this field, cybercrimes and should carry out such tasks as prevention, detection and elimination of cybercrimes.

Now this issue has become a focus of special attention all over the world. Also, each country is developing appropriate measures within its internal capabilities in terms of its interests. In particular, in our country, a lot of attention is paid to the issues of information security at the level of state policy. A number of regulatory documents are being adopted. In particular, the Law "On Cybersecurity" was developed in Uzbekistan in 2022. The purpose of the new law is to regulate relations in the field of cyber security in the cyberspace of the Republic of Uzbekistan; Determining the powers, rights and obligations of the authorized body in the field of cyber security; Creating a legal framework for the promotion and development of the national cyber security industry: taking measures to support the state, training cyber security experts, creating a national operating system and software, etc. [4].

Also, a cybercrime prevention system will be created in Uzbekistan. This is stated in the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev "On the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026". In this, the main directions of ensuring the cyber security of the "Uz" domain zone internet space are determined. Comprehensive tasks for the protection of e-government, energy, digital economy systems and other areas related to important information infrastructure will be created.

It is also planned to revise the criminal liability for cybercrime. The system of monitoring cyberattacks and threats in the information field will be improved. This will expand the technical infrastructure of the unified cyber security network. It is planned to further accelerate the activity of the "Innovations in Cybernetics IT Park". It is envisaged to

ensure the training of young people on the basics of cyber security on the basis of digital technology training centers of the IT-park and to hold republic-wide contests on the detection of cyber-attacks among students every year[5].

In today's era of globalization, cyber security and cyber weapons are essential in the use of the Internet, and it is important to ensure the security of various types of foreign information, including the illegal acquisition of information. To do this, cyber security experts and information security analysts are very necessary. For this purpose, special attention is being paid to the training of personnel who have mastered modern programming technologies in our country. At the moment, the project "One million programmers" is being implemented in our country. Today in the world there is a high demand for personnel - programmers who can introduce digitization, mobilization, artificial intelligence. Because of the infrastructure that supports the digital economy, and the huge investment in the ICT sector, cyber security can only be ensured by programmers who can effectively use electronic capabilities.

Currently, digitization processes are developing rapidly all over the world. Digitization processes are making it easier for services and information of many industries to move from reality to cyberspace, thereby providing services to users remotely at any time. Cyberspace continues to expand and form a large database. Depending on the asset value of cyberspace data, the risk of those involved in it is also increasing. This creates threats to the interests of individuals, society and the state.

As cybercrime is on the rise, there are more and more cases where their actions lead to interruptions in the operation of information systems and (or) violations of the openness, integrity and free use of information in them. If threats and hazards are not prevented, they can have very harmful negative consequences. And cyber security is the main direction of protecting the interests of the individual, society and the state from such cyber situations.

When developing measures to ensure cyber security, it is important to have some information about threats and risks. The role of cyber intelligence to detect and stop incidents before they happen is invaluable.

Even today, attempts are made to spread their moral corruption, immorality, and extremist ideas through various information and communication media, to destroy the meaning of our youth, to weaken them ideologically, to influence them with false ideas, and to cause acts of moral corruption among them.

Scientist T. Thomas, who conducted research on the problem of cyber threats, explains that information is the main tool of ideological influence as follows: "Information resources should be protected from others in the same way as nuclear weapons are protected; information resources can break the balance of power; since information attacks are not very visible in their initial stage, it is not always possible to apply measures to prevent them; information attacks do not pose an environmental threat, therefore, organizing an information attack on the enemy is more effective than using nuclear weapons; information practices can derail the country's economy; information attacks are an effective way to weaken the national spirit in people; information attacks can distort the existing reality and cause the country to make wrong decisions or disrupt the decision-making process»[6].

Today, the interference of mass communication and information media in the personal life of a person, in which the impact on the human mind using the press, radio, and television, has cast doubt on the dreams and hopes that the comprehensive control of information over

people's lives will realize the best ideals of people's lives [7]. The danger of the explosion provided by information technology is no less than that of overpopulation or pollution of the planet earth. Today, information resources have begun to play a leading role in social, economic and political life.

Under such circumstances, understanding national security in a modern spirit, determining the national interests of our country as a sum of the balance of the interests of the individual, society and the state, finding their optimal balance in the information field led to the formation of opinions about the actualization of the issue of information psychological security of the individual. Ensuring the security of the state and society of Uzbekistan is closely related to ensuring the information and psychological security of the individual. Therefore, in the concept of national security of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the following are distinguished as the interests that determine the state of personal security: realization of constitutional rights and freedoms, ensuring personal security, improving the quality and level of life, spiritual and intellectual development of people and citizens. Among the most important national interests of Uzbekistan in the field of information, in particular, compliance with the constitutional rights and freedoms of citizens to receive and use information [8]. In this respect, raising the issue of ensuring the informational psychological safety of young people and finding its solution in accordance with modern conditions and the needs of social practice determines the need to develop the next important factor - theoretically methodologically substantiating the methods and means of ensuring the informational psychological safety of the individual. Taking into account the specific aspects of the object and essence of information impact on a person, the system of psychological protection of a person serves as the basis for ensuring the psychological security of personal information in modern conditions [9].

The relevance of this problem in modern conditions has been fully understood in recent years. It has been found in many studies that without constant information communication, the full-blooded development of a person, social groups and society as a whole cannot be carried out moderately [10]. In this regard, the hidden aspect of information communication processes, which poses a real and growing threat to the development of individuals and society, has been neglected. Although the formation of the new foundations of the information society has been achieved to a certain extent in many developed countries, the process of its further improvement continues [11]. Information society is based on the idea of freedom of information, free exchange of information and freedom of speech in the field of communication. Today we are witnessing the information process. Because the process of informatization, which is observed on a global scale and finds its expression in the processes of integration, began to penetrate into all spheres of human life.

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